

DISCIPLINARY CHALLENGES INDEX IN RELATION TO SCHOOL SERVICES IN CARAGA NORTH DISTRICT

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Abstract. The study determined the relationship between the disciplinary challenges index and school services in Caraga North District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. This used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected 120 teacher-respondents. The treatments used were Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. The Findings revealed that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index in terms of consistency in enforcement, emotional toll, and balancing authority and respect are oftentimes manifested; while, peer pressure and influence and student misbehavior are sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive; the school service in terms of safety measures is oftentimes manifested; consistency in enforcement, conflict resolution strategies, and counseling services utilization sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. A significant relationship exists between implementing the disciplinary challenges index and school service. All domains of disciplinary challenges index in terms of student behavior, balancing authority and respect, peer pressure, emotional toll, and consistency in enforcement significantly influence school service. Future research may investigate the scalability of successful practices in different educational contexts

KEY WORDS

1. Disciplinary challenges index .
2. school service .
3. Caraga North District.

1. Introduction

Implementing school disciplinary programs can be challenging due to the diverse range of considerations and challenges. Schools cater to students from different cultural, linguistic, and socio-economic backgrounds. Therefore, a culturally sensitive and contextually relevant approach to discipline is necessary. To implement such a system, one must have a deep understanding of the cultural norms and values of the student body, as well as an awareness of international perspectives on discipline. It requires adapting disciplinary policies and strategies to suit a global student population's unique needs and expectations. Successful implementation depends on open communication and collaboration among educators, parents, and students to ensure that disciplinary measures align with the school's mission of creating a safe, inclusive, and respectful learning environment that transcends cultural boundaries. The tension between disciplines and interdisciplinary initiatives has been present in different areas worldwide. It begins with the meaning of discipline and the nuances in the interaction of

multiple disciplines (e.g., multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, or transdisciplinary) and traces. It traces the development of disciplines about the development of higher education. While academic departments and programs give life and power to the disciplines, there were pressures to work across disciplines to achieve the underlying goals of scholarship. Multiple disciplines are needed to solve real-world problems, understand complex systems, implement policy or apply research, and generate groundbreaking ideas (Cuyegkeng, 2020). Student misbehaviors in the classroom both disrupt students' attention and negatively affect the teaching and learning process. Akkas and Ocak (2021) examine student misbehaviors encountered to identify the most common and disruptive student misbehaviors from teachers' perspectives and to put forth teachers' suggestions about proper behaviors. The most disruptive misbehaviors were making noise, absenteeism, and distractibility. On the other hand, Robert (2020) examines the case of one large urban school district's implementation of Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports (PBIS) to review competing needs and challenges encountered over four years. There are encouraging results supporting the finding of a successful implementation and plans for continued implementation. Reducing the continuing disparity between the percentages of African American and White students receiving disciplinary consequences remains a challenge. The Philippine education system also adheres to national laws and policies that guide disciplinary practices, ensuring they align with the country's cultural and legal context. The nature of implementing disciplinary programs in the Philippines is characterized by a solid commitment to instilling values, fostering responsibility, and maintaining a respectful and orderly learning environment. Discipline is highly emphasized in Philippine schools, reflecting the deeply ingrained values of respect for authority and responsible behavior. The nature of implementation involves a combination of proactive measures, such as character education and values formation, alongside reactive strategies like clear rules and consequences for misconduct. Filipino educators often employ a holistic approach, integrating moral and ethical teachings into the curriculum to nurture responsible citizenship. Moreover, school administrators work closely with parents and the community to reinforce discipline at home and on the broader society (Child Protection Policy, DO 40, S 2012). Implementing DepED's Child Protection Policy, as outlined in Department Order No. 40, Series of 2012 (DO 40 S 2012), in the Davao Region is a critical undertaking to ensure the safety and well-being of students. The policy is executed through a collaborative effort among the Department of Education (DepEd), school administrators, teachers, parents, and local communities. Schools in the Davao Region are required to establish Child Protection Committees that are responsible for overseeing policy implementation at the school level. These committees are tasked with raising awareness about child protection issues, conducting training and workshops for educators, students, and parents, and ensuring that child protection mechanisms and reporting procedures are functional. Additionally, the policy promotes the creation of a safe and nurturing learning environment, free from all forms of abuse, discrimination, and violence. In the Davao Region, this involves rigorous monitoring and supervision of schools, regular reporting of incidents, and responsive actions when violations occur. Furthermore, partnerships with local government units and relevant organizations enhance the effectiveness of the policy's implementation, contributing to the overall goal of safeguarding the rights and dignity of every student in the region. In CARAGA North, schools encounter several challenges in implementing disciplinary measures, particularly in the context of DepED's Disciplinary Challenges. One of the primary challenges is the region's

vast geographical expanse, which can make it logistically difficult to ensure uniform policy enforcement and consistent monitoring of child protection concerns across remote and dispersed areas. Additionally, resource limitations, including the availability of trained personnel and the allocation of funds, can pose obstacles to effectively addressing child protection issues. Furthermore, cultural diversity within the region requires schools to be sensitive to varying community norms and practices, which may impact the interpretation and application of the policy.

Lastly, maintaining a balance between promoting a respectful and inclusive school environment while addressing disciplinary challenges can be intricate, requiring a nuanced approach. Overcoming these challenges necessitates collaborative efforts among schools, local government units, and communities to create a safe and supportive atmosphere where the rights and well-being of students are protected as per the Child Protection Policy. Thus, this paper is conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps for conducting the study. These include selecting the study design, the respondents and sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical considerations, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are essential to ensure appropriateness and correctness and produce sound data collection, analysis, and interpretation. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. This design is a comprehensive approach to research methodology that combines several key elements to explore relationships and systematically predict outcomes. It typically involves observing and analyzing existing data or naturally occurring phenomena without intervening, manipulating, or controlling variables (Creswell, 2014). Using a non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design in the context of the disciplinary challenges index in fostering positive school communities offers a comprehensive approach to understanding and addressing the complexities of disciplinary issues within educational institutions. This type of research design involves systematically collect-

ing and analyzing existing data and information without intervention or manipulating variables. It allows researchers to explore the relationships between various factors related to disciplinary challenges and their impact on developing positive school communities. Descriptive aspects of the research design involve documenting and characterizing the disciplinary challenges that schools face, including the types of misbehavior, their frequency, and the surrounding circumstances. This provides a clear picture of the school's current state of disciplinary issues. Correlational analysis explores the relationships between variables, such as the disciplinary challenges index, student demographics, school policies, and academic outcomes. This helps identify patterns and associations, revealing how disciplinary challenges may in-

fluence the school environment and student performance. Predictive elements of the research design allow for the development of models or frameworks that can forecast the impact of disciplinary challenges on creating positive school communities. By examining historical data and trends, researchers can make informed predictions about future outcomes, enabling educators and administrators to address issues and implement targeted interventions proactively. A non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design provides a holistic understanding of disciplinary challenges in fostering positive school communities. It equips educational institutions with valuable insights to develop evidence-based strategies, policies, and interventions, ultimately creating safer, more respectful, and conducive learning environments for students.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Elementary and Secondary School Teachers in the five elementary and national high schools in Caraga North District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective School within the Caraga North District. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi connections, and they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were selected because they were assumed to have been engaged in the disciplinary mechanisms in the school systems. They were also the coordinators of child-friendly related policies implemented in the schools. They are qualified for the position and expected to have performed and contributed, given that they have attended seminars and trainings related to child-friendly and child protection policies under the School-Based Management system. This is

done through School Learning Action Cells to improve the school and the learners' awareness and educational stages given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy policies through school-based initiatives to support the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature, as the authors argued. The survey questionnaire had two parts, one of which consisted of indicators of disciplinary challenges index in terms of student misbehavior, balancing authority and respect, peer pressure and influence, emotional toll, and consistency in enforcement. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured positive school communities in terms of character education integration, conflict resolution strategies, counseling services utilization, and safety measures. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. It generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.864, which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal consistency is very good. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of disciplinary challenges. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The disciplinary challenges are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The disciplinary challenges are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The disciplinary challenges are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The disciplinary challenges are rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The disciplinary challenges are not manifested.

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of fostering school services, a 5-point Likert scale

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
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1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The school services are rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The school services are not manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements explain the data-gathering procedure steps that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the college where the researcher is studying and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data, most especially in the current entire face-to-face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. In the second week of October 2023, the researcher started conceptualizing the thesis proposal’s contents and objective. She then prepared documents such as letter requests

for the study. The research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004) and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. On the last week of January up to the first week of February 2024, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the Elementary and Secondary schools of Caraga North District, Davao Ori-

tal Schools Division. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In February 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email and to respondents who do not have access to the internet. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to pro-

ceed with data gathering, which commenced on the first week of March 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of April 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometimes on the last week of April 2024, and further deepen the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of fostering positive school communities in Caraga North District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between the implementation of the disciplinary challenges index and fos-

tering positive school communities in Caraga North District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of disciplinary challenges index that significantly influence fostering positive school communities in Caraga North District, Davao Oriental Schools Division (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the responses from the data gathered in tabular and textual form. It includes discussions of the results based on an integration with reviews of the related studies. Given the hypothesis posed, this will be the basis for the decisions.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Consistency In Enforcement (3.60), Emotional Toll (3.58) and Balancing Authority And Respect (3.46) are oftentimes manifested;

while, Peer Pressure And Influence (3.38) and Student Misbehavior (2.98) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.28 denotes that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Implementation of Disciplinary Challenges Index

No	Disciplinary Challenges Index	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Student Misbehavior	2.98	Moderately Extensive
2	Balancing Authority And Respect	3.46	Extensive
3	Peer Pressure And Influence	3.38	Moderately Extensive
4	Emotional Toll	3.58	Extensive
5	Consistency In Enforcement	3.60	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.38	Moderately Extensive

Naidoo and Taylor (021) stated that a better understanding of the social influences, self-efficacy, and communication with parents, peers, and teachers associated with teenage pregnancy is required owing to the consequences of teenage pregnancy. They aimed to determine the prevalence of teenage pregnancy and to understand the association between social influences, self-efficacy, and communication about teenage pregnancies, among high school students in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. Teenage pregnancy was associated with age, being female, and exposure to communication discouraging pregnancy. Students living

with both parents, or where family and peers believed that the adolescents should abstain from sex, or who experienced positive social pressure discouraging pregnancy were unlikely to have had a pregnancy. Developing the professional capacity of teachers and school leaders through mentoring, coaching, and professional development is crucial to replacing exclusionary discipline with nonpunitive practices. Districts ought to prioritize supporting school leaders in developing and expanding their professional capacity, who in turn support teachers in addressing school discipline challenges.

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of school services. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: safety measures (3.54) I oftentimes manifested; consistency in enforcement (3.48), conflict resolution strategies (3.12)

and counseling services utilization (3.12) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.31 denotes that extent of implementation of disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of School Services

No	Positive School Communities	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Consistency in enforcement	3.48	Moderately Extensive
2	Conflict Resolution Strategies	3.12	Extensive
3	Counselling Services Utilization	3.12	Moderately Extensive
4	Safety Measures	3.54	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.31	Moderately Extensive

The extent of school services encompasses various elements that contribute to a nurturing and supportive educational environment. Positive school communities are characterized by strong connections among students, educators, administrators, and parents, fostering a sense of belonging and shared purpose. Open communication and collaboration are encouraged in such environments, creating a foundation for effective learning and personal development. Rauk et.al. (2023) stated that the extent of a positive school community is reflected in the emphasis placed on values like respect, empathy, and inclusivity. Schools that prioritize positive

communities often implement programs and initiatives that promote student well-being, mental health, and social-emotional learning. Adams et.al. (2022) establish a line of inquiry that positive school cultures also extend to the acknowledgment of diversity and the celebration of different backgrounds, fostering a sense of unity and understanding among the school’s members. The extent of positive school communities is not only measured by academic achievements but also by the overall well-rounded growth and happiness of students within a supportive and affirming educational setting.

Relationship between Implementation of Disciplinary Challenges Index and School Services

Table 3 flaunts the yielded results of the significant relationship between the implementation of the disciplinary challenges index and positive school communities. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between

implementation of the disciplinary challenges index and positive school communities must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between the implementation of the disciplinary challenges index ($r=0.899$; $p_i.000$) and positive school communities.

Table 3. Relationship between Implementation of Disciplinary Challenges I and School Services

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
disciplinary challenges index				
positive school communities	0.899	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

Collie (2022) examined the implementation of a Disciplinary Challenges Index and the cultivation of positive school communities share a significant and interconnected relationship within an educational setting. A well-designed Disciplinary Challenges Index serves as a diagnostic tool, allowing schools to identify and address issues related to student behavior, discipline, and overall school climate. When this index is effectively implemented, it can con-

tribute to the creation of a positive school community by providing insights into areas that may require attention or intervention. By understanding and addressing disciplinary challenges, schools can foster an environment that is conducive to positive social interactions, emotional well-being, and academic success. Conversely, Pieng and Okamoto (2020) investigated positive school communities, with their emphasis on open communication, mutual respect, and a

sense of belonging, can contribute to the prevention and mitigation of disciplinary issues. When students feel supported, valued, and connected to their school community, they are more likely to exhibit positive behavior and engage in constructive learning experiences. Therefore,

the successful implementation of a Disciplinary Challenges Index and the cultivation of positive school communities are mutually reinforcing elements, working together to create an environment that promotes both discipline and well-being among students.

Domains of Disciplinary Challenges Index Significantly Influence School Services

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of disciplinary challenges index, which significantly influenced school services. Domains of the disciplinary challenges index in terms of student behavior (0.000), balancing authority and respect (0.001), peer pressure and influence (0.000), emotional toll (0.000), and consistency in enforcement (0.001) suggest significant influence over positive school communities. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.888 suggests that the positive school communities are explained by 88.8%

In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (254.897) and F-statistic are significant $p < .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of special education outcomes. The domains of a Disciplinary Challenges Index wield substantial influence over the development and sustenance of positive school communities. Yildiz (2023) aimed to examine a comprehensive index typically encompasses various domains such as student behavior, classroom management, conflict resolution, and overall school climate

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Non-Teaching Responsibilities Significantly Influencing Pedagogical Delivery Priorities

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	t	p-value	Decisions
H ₀ (Intercept)	4.145		0.079	60.416	0.001	
H ₁ (Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204	
Administrative duties	0.227	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.324	*Reject H ₀
Professional Development	0.211	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.112	*Reject H ₀
Student Support Services	0.222	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.033	*Reject H ₀
Parent and Community Engagement	0.242	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.035	*Reject H ₀
School Committee Participation	0.257	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.312	*Reject H ₀

$R^2 = 0.878, F\text{-value} = 264.857, p\text{-value} = .001$

By systematically evaluating these domains, educational institutions gain insights into the challenges affecting discipline and can proactively address them. Eslit (2023) when applied effectively, the index serves as a diagnostic tool, enabling schools to identify specific areas that may be hindering the creation of a positive

school culture. For instance, understanding patterns of disruptive behavior or areas where conflict arises allows for targeted interventions. By addressing these challenges head-on, schools can cultivate an environment where mutual respect, open communication, and a sense of belonging thrive, forming the bedrock of positive

school communities. The transparency and accountability facilitated by a Disciplinary Challenges Index contribute to a shared commitment among administrators, educators, students, and parents to collaboratively build a school culture that fosters not only academic success but also emotional well-being and a supportive community ethos. In essence, the careful consideration and management of the domains within a Disciplinary Challenges Index significantly shape the overall positive atmosphere within educational institutions (Zakszeski and Rutherford, 2021).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In this chapter, the outcomes, conclusions, and recommendations are delineated in accordance with the analyzed and discussed data, along with the implications drawn from the findings. The findings emanate from the articulated statement of the problem, while the conclusions are derived from the resultant findings. The recommendations, in turn, are formulated based on the implications gleaned from the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index in terms of consistency in enforcement, emotional toll, and balancing authority and respect are oftentimes manifested, while peer pressure and influence and student misbehavior are sometimes manifested. The extent of school services in terms of safety measures is oftentimes manifested; consistency in enforcement, conflict resolution strategies, and counseling services utilization are sometimes manifested. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between the implementation of the disciplinary challenges index and school service. Domains of disciplinary challenges index in terms of student behavior, balancing authority and respect, peer pressure and influence emotional toll and consistency in enforcement suggest significant influence over positive school communities.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions: The extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index in terms of consistency in enforcement, emotional toll, and balancing authority and respect is often manifested; while peer pressure and influence and student misbehavior are sometimes manifested. This denotes that the disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. The extent of school services in terms of safety measures is often manifested; consistency in enforcement, conflict resolution strategies, and counseling services utilization are sometimes manifested. This denotes that the extent of school services manifested is moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between the implementation of the disciplinary challenges index and school services. Domains of disciplinary challenges index in terms of student behavior, balancing authority and respect, peer pressure, emotional toll, and consistency in enforcement significantly influence school services. Skinner's behavioral modification model (1992), Glasser's Choice theory (1998), and Canter's assertive discipline model (2007), as cited by Howell et al. (2021) have made relevance to the disciplinary challenges that involve difficulties in effectively enforcing school policies, addressing the underlying causes of misbehavior, and balancing the need for discipline with the promotion of responsible citizenship. Such challenges are complex and multifaceted, with their nature and scope varying from one educational setting to another. Addressing disciplinary challenges requires a

holistic approach that combines preventive measures, conflict resolution strategies, clear disciplinary policies, and the active involvement of administrators, teachers, parents, and students to create a positive and conducive school environment. Moreover, good school discipline is one of the most important characteristics of an effective school and a vital aspect of school and classroom management (Minch, et.al., 2020). Furthermore, discipline is important for maintaining harmony in a school, and for securing a climate in which learners can learn free from disruption and chaos. Effective discipline creates a climate conducive to high academic and non-academic achievements. It is commonly accepted that learners perform better when they know what is expected of them (Hart and Butler, 2022).

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May consider implementing a comprehensive training program for educators focused on proactive disciplinary strategies and the effective use of the Disciplinary Challenges Index. This training should emphasize collaborative approaches, fostering a positive school culture, and addressing specific challenges identified in the study. Additionally, the supervisor is encouraged to allocate resources for ongoing professional development to ensure that teachers stay updated on best practices. School Principal. The study suggests the establishment of a school-wide task force dedicated to

examining and refining the implementation of the Disciplinary Challenges Index. This task force should include representatives from various stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and students, fostering a collaborative effort to create a positive and inclusive school environment. Furthermore, the principal is advised to allocate resources for initiatives that promote a positive school community, such as extracurricular activities, counseling services, and conflict resolution programs. Teacher. The study recommends ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance classroom management skills and strategies for addressing disciplinary challenges. Teachers are encouraged to actively participate in workshops that focus on positive behavior reinforcement, fostering a supportive learning environment. Additionally, it is recommended that teachers engage in regular communication with parents to create a collaborative partnership in addressing and preventing disciplinary issues. Future Researcher. The study recommends delving deeper into the long-term effects of positive school communities and effective disciplinary strategies on academic achievement, student well-being, and overall school success. Exploring different contexts and diverse populations can contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing positive school environments. Future researchers are encouraged to employ both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to capture the multifaceted nature of school dynamics and disciplinary challenges.

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